

ISic3128

I.Sicily inscription 3128

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

(?)

Material

marble

Object

plaque

Editor

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Autopsy

2014-09-09 (Prag)

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico Regionale Paolo Orsi

Physical Description

Thin fragment of grey marble, intact along the bottom edge, broken on the other three sides. The reverse is finished smooth.

Dimensions

Height 7 cm

Width 11 cm

Depth 1.5 cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Somewhat irregular, deep cut letters with pronounced terminal serifs. Lunate sigma and epsilon, xi formed somewhat after the fashion of the numeral 3, omicron in line 2 tiny.

Letter heights:

Line 1: incomplete mm

Lines 2-3: 8-10 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: not measured mm

Text

1. [---][---]

2. [---]πλους καὶ ἐξεῖ[---]

3. [---]υριδι πολυτε[---]

Apparatus

Text from autopsy

Final character is not clearly an I (as read by Manganaro) but could also be N, although the most visible diagonal is superficial damage

The π has a second horizontal stroke at the midpoint; a short vertical stroke is visible at the right-hand edge of the stone

Translation

Commentary

Rediscovered in the Museum stores in 2014, having not been seen since initial publication by Manganaro. Inventory number not yet identified. The text looks rather later than the Hellenistic date proposed by Manganaro, who published it in the context of the Hellenistic oracular verse texts from Akrai, and seems more likely to be of the Roman imperial period.

Digital identifiers:

TM 645469

PHI 333767

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 31.0845

Manganaro, G. 1981. L'oracolo di Maie per una carestia in territorio siracusano. *ASNP*. ser. 3, vol. 11: 1069-1082. At 1078-1079 ph

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Photo J. Prag, Aut. Assessorato Beni Culturali Regione Siciliana n.10681 del
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